

Sample Size Calculation for Continuous and Discrete Data

Louangrath, P. I. ★

About the Author

★Louangrath, P.I. is an Assistant Professor in Business Administration at Bangkok University, Bangkok, Thailand. He could be reached by email at: Ajarnmahaved@gmail.com & Lecturepedia@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The purpose of this paper is to provide a practical guidance to researcher in social science on sample size determination. Sample size calculation is a basic and indispensable requisite for applied research in social science. Most research in social science is about population studies. In population studies, researchers could only study the sample of the population because detailed examination of the population is not feasible. In order for the sample to represent the population, a minimum sample must be obtained. Thus, minimum sample determination becomes a critical requisite in survey collection, interviews, or data collection. In this paper, we present minimum sample calculation methods for continuous and discrete data in non-time series scenarios. The data came from randomly generated values by using Excel command: `rand()*100` for test sample sizes of $n = 5, 10, 20, 30, 50, 100, 200, 300, 400, 500,$ and $1,000$. We proposed a new minimum sample size method that consistently produces $n = 30$.

Key words:

Continuous data, discrete data, power, sample, sample size

JEL CODE: C10, C13, C14, C46, E27, G11, G17

CITATION:

Louangrath, P.I. (2019). "Sample Size Calculation for Continuous and Discrete Data." *Inter. J. Res. Methodol. Soc. Sci.*, Vol., 5, No. 4: pp. 44-56. (Oct. – Dec. 2019); ISSN: 2415-0371. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.3877623

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Most research in social science deals with population studies. Population studies require the use of sample. Many social science journals make compulsory for authors to report certain key estimates which are commonly used in sample size calculations (Schulz *et al.*, 2010). The findings learned from the sample (observation) are inferred onto to the population. This inference must pass two tests: reliability and validity. Reliability is defined as consistency. Consistency means that repeated measurements produce similar results. Validity means accuracy of measurement or minimal error between the expected and observed values. The sample size required to achieve these two requirements is called *minimum sample size*. There is a risk that the sample does not represent the population. This risk is reduced for 99% confidence levels and increased for 90% or lower levels of confidence (Gupta and Kapoor 1970 and Singh and Masuku, 2012).

Sample size calculation is important to research. Emphasize the significance of sample size include animal studies by Shah (2011), cluster randomized controlled trials (CRCT) for fixed number of clusters (Karla, 2011), medical research (Sathian, 2010) and sample size and power analysis in medical research (Zodey, 2010). medical science (Macfarlane, 2003) and health services research (Wood, 1999). Macfarlane (2003) asserted that sample size calculations is essential part of a study protocol for submission to ethical committees, research funding bodies and some peer reviewed journals.

Sathian (2010) asserted that sample size determination is a difficult process. Statistical power is analogous to the sensitivity of a diagnostic test (Browner and Newman 1987). Many published clinical studies have low statistical power due to inadequate sample size (Moher *et al.*, 1994 and Freiman *et al.*, 1978).

Minimum sample size determination is shrouded with uncertainty. Although we accept the assertion that the “purpose of the study, population size, the risk of selecting a “bad” sample, and the allowable sampling error.” (Israel, 1992), but we reject the argument that “the estimation of the minimum sample size required for any study is not a single unique method.” (Gotay, 2010).

There is a need in all fields of social science that a common and unified method for sample size determination be available. No matter if the population is known or unknown, no matter whether the data is discrete or continuous, this paper attempts to provide a practical method for minimum sample size calculation. Many researchers agree that a sample size of 30 is ideal; however, the literature is sparse on how to verify that the sample size is 30 or how the number 30 is obtained. This paper provides a method on how to obtain a minimum sample size of 30 in all cases.

We note that is a distinction between quantitative and qualitative research. For purposes of sample size calculation, we argue that quantitative and qualitative distinction is boiled down to the difference between continuous and discrete data. Quantitative research mainly deals with continuous data. Qualitative research mainly deals with discrete data. Under this distinction, we dispense with all claims in the literature that cast uncertainty to sample size determination in qualitative research.

In qualitative research, sample size determination, it is also unsettled and is highly influenced by the investigator's subjectivity (Sandelowski, 1995). It is a common practice of keep adding more participants until a saturation point is reached (Glaser, 1965). There is no definitive guidance on sample size determination in qualitative research (Francis *et al.*, 2010; Guest *et al.*, 2006; and Wright *et al.*, 2011). There are suggestions on how many samples should be taken, but there is no definitive method for calculating sample size for qualitative research (Onwuegbuzie and Leech, 2007; Fugard and Pott, 2015). In this paper, we debunk this uncertain for sample size determination in qualitative research by asserting that qualitative research deals with discrete data. As such, a sample size determination for discrete data may be used.

We eliminate the distinction between continuous and discrete data under the logic that for discrete data, as the sample size tends towards infinity, the distribution becomes continuous. Under this ideal condition, the distinction between continuous and discrete data diminished. This argument was asserted in Papoulis *et al.*, (2002) and Feller (1968) who asserted that:

$$\binom{n}{k} p^k q^{n-k} \cong \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi npq}} \exp\left(-\left(\frac{(k-np)^2}{2npq}\right)\right) \quad (1)$$

For binary or discrete data, we expect to achieve normal distribution under the deMoivre-Laplace Theorem under the following condition:

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \Pr\left(\frac{X-np}{\sqrt{npq}}\right) \geq Z \quad (2)$$

where X = total success of the category of interest, n = number of observation, $p = (s+1)/(n+2)$, and Z = critical value whose corresponding percentage probability may be found in the Z table or calculating by:

$$F(Z) = \frac{1}{1 + \exp\left(-\sqrt{\pi}\left(\beta_1 Z^5 + \beta_2 Z^3 + \beta_3 Z\right)\right)} \quad (3)$$

where $Z = (x - \bar{x})/s$, $\beta_1 = 0.0004406$, $\beta_2 = 0.0418198$, and $\beta_3 = 0.90000000$. Finally, under ideal condition, all data should normalized, and we expect the data to achieve normal distribution according to:

$$f(x | \mu, \sigma^2) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi\sigma^2}} \exp\left(-\frac{(x-\mu)^2}{2\sigma^2}\right) \quad (4)$$

The use of normal distribution as the reference or ideal condition to determine sample size is well documented (Devane and *et al.*, 2004). The element of sample size determination include the type of data and it distribution (Julios, 2004).

2.0 LITERATURE

Minimum sample size remains unsettled in the field. There is a need for a more generalized and stable method for determining sample size. We examined this uncertainty expressed by many researchers. A review of the literature in this discipline can provide supervision about typical sample sizes that are used (Glenn, 1992). We conclude that the literature lacks a fixed or generalized sample size equation that would allow common sample size for all cases. This paper addresses this gap in the literature.

Sudman (1976) suggested a minimum of 100 elements be collected for each major group or subgroup in the sample and for each minor subgroup, a sample of 20 to 50 elements was necessary. Kish (Kish, 1965) advocated the use of 30 to 200 elements when the attribute presents 20 to 80 percent if the distribution approaches normality. Some attempted to explain sample size calculation according to certain criteria. Three criteria are needed to determine sample size: the level of precision, the level of confidence or risk, and the degree of variability in the attributes being measured (Miaoulis and Michener, 1976).

Sample size literature generally uses the population as the indicator for sample size determination approach. If the population is known (finite population), the Yamane method is used. Under the Yamane method, the sample size determination depends on known population and a

specified precision or error level. Under this method, it is assumed that the data is normally distributed. The Yamane equation is given by:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e^2)} \quad (5)$$

where N = population size and e is the error level (Yamane, 1967; p. 886). The Yamane equation generally produces sample size of approximately 400.

A second general scenario involves a non-finite population where the total population is unknown. In this scenario, it is imperative that the investigator takes an initial test sample. The descriptive and inferential statistics from this initial test sample will a calculation for the minimum sample. The minimum sample for the project is given by:

$$n = \left(\frac{Z\sigma}{E} \right)^2 \quad (6)$$

where Z is the critical value at a target confidence interval; σ is the expected standard deviation obtained by $\sigma = ((\bar{x} - \mu) / z) \sqrt{n}$ with $\mu = \bar{x} - T(S / \sqrt{n})$, and $E = \sigma / \sqrt{n}$. As we will later learn, this equation (5) produces unreliable result (*see* Table 1).

2.1 Confidence interval testing

This paper provides sample size to estimate confidence interval, and sample size used for testing hypothesis. Confidence level is the proportion of possible confidence intervals that contain the true value of the unknown population (Cox and Hinkley, 1974; Kendal and Stuart, 1973). It represents the proportion of the observed contains the population parameters. For example, a confidence interval of 95% means that 95% of the population parameters may be represented by the sample (Neyman, 1937). To clarify this point, Neyman wrote:

“It will be noticed that in the above description, the probability statements refer to the problems of estimation with which the statistician will be concerned in the future. In fact, I have repeatedly stated that the frequency of correct results will tend to α . Consider now the case when a sample is already drawn, and the calculations have given [particular limits]. Can we say that in this particular case the probability of the true value [falling between these limits] is equal to α ? The answer is obviously in the negative. The parameter is an unknown constant, and no probability statement concerning its value may be made...”

Confidence interval is the number obtained from the sample observations that claims to represent the population parameters, not about representation of the population in the sample (Greenland *et al.*, 2016). More recent clarification to avoid confusion was provided by Deborah Mayo (1981) who wrote:

“It must be stressed, however, that having seen the value [of the data], Neyman–Pearson theory never permits one to conclude that the specific confidence interval formed covers the true value of θ with either $(1 - \alpha)100\%$ probability or $(1 - \alpha)100\%$ degree of confidence. Seidenfeld's remark seems rooted in a (not uncommon) desire for Neyman–Pearson confidence intervals to provide something which they cannot legitimately provide; namely, a measure of the degree of probability, belief, or support that an unknown parameter value lies in a specific interval. Following Savage (1962), the

probability that a parameter lies in a specific interval may be referred to as a measure of final precision. While a measure of final precision may seem desirable, and while confidence levels are often (wrongly) interpreted as providing such a measure, no such interpretation is warranted. Admittedly, such a misinterpretation is encouraged by the word 'confidence'."

Hypothesis testing is the verification of a set of observations by a set of statistical rule (Stuart and Ord, 1999). A confidence interval is specified and the observed data is tested against that confidence interval. If the result exceeds the pre-specified interval, it is considered statistically significant (Rice, 2007). The threshold value used in statistical hypothesis testing is called test statistic. The test may be read against the test statistic based on observed confidence interval compared to the threshold confidence interval, i.e. 95%, or comparing the error to the present error level, i.e. 5%. Both confidence interval and error comparison lead to the same conclusion (Triola, 2001). This approach to hypothesis testing is called test of significance (Fisher, 1925).

Hypothesis testing is related to sample size. In order to test the hypothesis, one needs a set of observations. Observations are read from the sample. The question is what sample size is required to test the hypothesis? If the sample is too large, it may lead to waste of resources. If the sample is too small, it may not be used as a fair representation of the population. Thus, an ideal sample size is a minimum sample size.

The method for sample size calculation may also dictated by the type of data used in the research. There are two types of data: continuous and discrete. The data may be quantitative. Quantitative data are continuous and may be subjected to basic mathematical operations: addition, subtraction, multiplication and division. A second type of data is called discrete or dichotomous data. These data may be in a form of ordinal or nominal data. Nominal data are used for ranking purposes. Nominal data are used for identification purpose. For purposes of sample size calculation in this paper, we categorized the data into two kinds: continuous and non-continuous.

2.2 Statistical hypothesis testing

Statistical hypothesis testing uses the null hypothesis as the basis. The null hypothesis is the counter argument that the investigator must overcome. The null hypothesis is overcome by empirical evidence.

The objective is to reject the null hypothesis. The null hypothesis may be rejected if the test statistic exceeds the null hypothesis threshold or the p-value (error level) is less than the preset p-value. Since both approaches may be used to achieve the same end: rejecting the null hypothesis, this may be a source of confusion whether to use the test statistic value or the p-value (Nuzzo, 2014). There should not be such confusion because both achieve the same goal, the confidence approach uses the cumulative distribution function (CDF) value as the test value. The null hypothesis is rejected if $CDF(obs) > CDF^*$. Whereas, the p-value approach used $1 - CDF$ as the threshold value, the null hypothesis is rejected if the $p\text{-value} < 1 - CDF$ "The probability of rejecting the null hypothesis is a function of five factors: whether the test is one- or two tailed, the level of significance, the standard deviation, the amount of deviation from the null hypothesis, and the number of observations." (Bakan, 1966).

3.0 DATA AND METHODOLOGY

3.1 Initial test sample size generated by random values: $RAND()*100$

The data used in this paper came from random value generated by Microsoft Excel command: $RAND()*100$. We use the command to generate random values for various initial test sample sizes: $n(test) = 10, 30, 50, 100, 200, 300, 400, 500$ and 1000. We then obtained the descriptive and inferential statistics to calculate the sample size according to equations (6) – (11). The result is presented in Table 2.

Randomness means lack of predictable pattern; “while disorder is more probable in general, complete disorder is impossible” (Prömel, 2005). Efficient algorithms for simple random sampling had been developed (Meng, 2013). For example, the selection-rejection algorithm (Fan *et al.*, 1962), simple random sort algorithm (Sunter, 1977), and reservoir sampling algorithm (Vitter, 1985). However, in this paper, we find it adequate to accept random values generated by excel command: RAND()*100 to produce value between 0 and 100 as adequate for our seed numbers for initial test values. Some random generator takes the value between 0 and 1 (Sunter, 1977). However, for our purpose the values between 0 and 1 are not practicable sinxe most social science research uses survey whose response space may be greater then 1, i.e. Likert scale (1,2,3,4,5). For this reason, we modified excel command from RAND() to RAND()*100 to obtain the values between 0 and 100.

3.2 Sample size calculation for continuous data.

For continuous data, there are three approaches to sample size calculation for confidence interval and hypothesis testing. The first method for continuous data sample size calculation involves one sample testing. The sample size for estimating confidence interval for one sample is given Smith (1983), *see* equation (5). $n = (Z\sigma / E)^2$ where Z is the standard score given by $Z = (X_i - \bar{X}) / S$ and E is the standard error given by $E = \sigma / \sqrt{n}$. The corresponding sample size for hypothesis testing in this case is given by:

$$n = \left(\frac{Z_{1-\alpha/2} + Z_{1-\beta}}{ES} \right)^2 \tag{7}$$

where $ES = \frac{|\mu_1 - \mu_2|}{\sigma}$. The objective is to find the confidence interval for $CI = \mu$ and the null hypothesis is given by $H_0 : \mu = \mu_0$.

The second case for continuous data involves two independent samples and the use of confidence interval for $CI = \mu_1 - \mu_2$ where the null hypothesis is $H_0 : \mu_1 = \mu_2$. The sample size for confidence interval in this case is given by:

$$n = 2 \left(\frac{Z\sigma}{E} \right)^2 \tag{8}$$

The accompanying sample size for hypothesis testing is:

$$n = 2 \left(\frac{Z_{1-\alpha/2} + Z_{1-\beta}}{ES} \right)^2 \tag{8a}$$

where $ES = \frac{|\mu_1 - \mu_2|}{\sigma}$.

A thirds case for continuous data involves the two independent sample and the use of confidence interval for $CI = \mu_d$ where the null hypothesis is $H_0 : \mu_d = 0$. The sample size for confidence interval in this case is given by:

$$n = \left(\frac{Z\sigma_d}{E} \right)^2 \tag{9}$$

where $ES = \frac{\mu_d}{\sigma_d}$.

3.3 Sample size calculation for discrete data

For discrete data, we present two methods of calculating sample size for confidence interval estimate and for hypothesis testing. For confidence interval, the sample size calculation for one sample where the null hypothesis is $p = p_1$:

$$n = p - (1 - p) \left(\frac{Z}{E} \right)^2 \tag{10}$$

This approach is used for one sample discrete data where $p = (s + 1)/(n + 2)$, Z is the standard score level and E is the error level. The sample size for hypothesis testing of one independent sample is given by:

$$n = \left(\frac{Z_{1-\alpha/2} + Z_{1-\beta}}{ES} \right)^2 \tag{10a}$$

where $ES = \frac{p_1 - p_0}{\sqrt{p_1(1 - p_1)}}$.

A second case for discrete data involves two independent samples where the null hypothesis is $p_1 = p_2$. The minimum sample calculation for two-independent samples is given by:

$$n = [p_1(1 - p_1) + p_2(1 - p_2)] \left(\frac{Z}{E} \right)^2 \tag{11}$$

The sample size for hypothesis testing of two independent sample is given by:

$$n = 2 \left(\frac{Z_{1-\alpha/2} + Z_{1-\beta}}{ES} \right)^2 \tag{11a}$$

where $ES = \frac{|p_1 - p_2|}{\sqrt{p(1 - p)}}$.

3.3 Power and Sample

In hypothesis testing, the objective is to reject the null hypothesis. In our sample calculation, we provided sample for estimating confidence interval and sample for testing hypothesis. An adequate sample meets the minimum sample requirement. That sample must be able to provide power at a level so as to allow the investigator to reject the null hypothesis. A sample size that falls below minimum sample requisite would not be able to reject the null hypothesis. Rejecting the null

hypothesis in such a case would result in Type I error. There is a relationship between sample size and power.

Power is the probability of rejecting the null hypothesis. It is given by $1 - \beta$ where:

$$1 - \beta = \Pr(Z \geq z_{\alpha/2} | H_1) = 1 - \Pr(Z < z_{\alpha/2} | H_1) \quad (12)$$

By substituting the mean of Z for both sides, we have:

$$\beta = \Pr \left(Z - \frac{\delta}{\sigma \sqrt{\frac{1}{n_0} + \frac{1}{n_1}}} < z_{\alpha/2} - \frac{\delta}{\sigma \sqrt{\frac{1}{n_0} + \frac{1}{n_1}}} \right) \quad (13)$$

The standard unit of power is given by:

$$Z_{1-\beta} = z_{\alpha/2} - \frac{\delta}{\sigma \sqrt{\frac{1}{n_0} + \frac{1}{n_1}}} \quad (14)$$

where $\delta = \mu_1 - \mu_0$ and the mean Z score is $\bar{Z} = \frac{\delta}{\sigma \sqrt{\frac{1}{n_0} + \frac{1}{n_1}}}$ with $\Pr(Z \leq -z_{\alpha/2} | H_1) \cong 0$.

4.0 FINDINGS AND ANALYSIS

We present our findings in two parts. In section 4.1, we present the estimate of sample size under equations (6) – (9) for continuous data and (10) to (11) for discrete data. We point out the problem of conventional sample size determination equation as being unstable in producing minimum sample size. The initial test sample to obtain the descriptive and inferential statistics to work out these equations influenced the final result. Different initial test samples produced different final sample size. We find this weakness as an obstruction to sample size generalizability. In section 4.2, we proposed a generalized sample size calculation method by taking equation (6) as the general form and modifying it by dividing the result of equation (6) by k initial test sample and multiplying the result by 4π . The result is a consistent 34.19 for all cases of continuous data regardless of the size of the initial test sample. This size of 34.19 is adjusted to 30 by subtracting a factor of $(1 + \pi - 0.05)$.

Under equation (6), $n = ((Z\sigma)/E)^2$ for continuous data, the sample size is not stable when the initial test sample differs. When the $n(\text{test}) = 10, 30, 50, 100, 200, 300, 400, 500$ and 1000 , the corresponding minimum sample size are: 54.45, 81.68, 136.13, 272.25, 544.50, 816.75, 1,089.00, 1,361.25, and 2,722.50, respectively.

Under equation (7) for continuous data, $n = 2((Z\sigma)/E)^2$, when the $n(\text{test}) = 10, 30, 50, 100, 200, 300, 400, 500$ and 1000 , the corresponding minimum sample sizes are: 54.44, 163.07, 272.67, 543.34, 1,089.43, 1,631.92, 2,182.45, 2,711.27, and 5,400.92, respectively.

Under equation (8) for continuous data, $n = ((Z\sigma_d)/ES)^2$ where $ES = \mu_d / \sigma_d$, when the $n(\text{test}) = 10, 30, 50, 100, 200, 300, 400, 500$ and 1000 , the corresponding minimum sample sizes are: 1,308.77, 985.14, 945.56, 898.98, 897.05, 894.38, 965.61, 760.47, and 756.06, respectively.

We also find similar problems with sample size equation for discrete data. Under equation (10), $n = [p - (1 - p)](Z / E)^2$ and equation (11) for discrete data, $n = [p_1(1 - p_1) + p_2(1 - p_2)](Z / E)^2$ produces sample size of 217.80 and 522.72 assuming that $p = 0.60$ and $q = 0.40$. A fair coin assumption of $p = 0.50$ and $q = 0.50$ will not work because in equation (10) the result would be zero.

From our estimate of sample size for purposes of confidence interval determination under equations (6) to (9) for continuous data, and (10) and (11) for discrete data, we conclude that these conventional sample size equation did not produce stable sample size. The size of the initial test sample influences the final sample size result. In equation (15), we uses equation (6) or the Smith's sample size equation, as a starting point to obtain a stable result of sample size at $n = 30$ for all cases regardless of the size of the initial test sample.

We reject the assertion that more complex equations are necessary for calculating sample sizes when comparing means (Rosner, 2000) and proportions (Fleiss 1981) of unequal group sizes or in any cases. We proposed a general sample size equation that may be used in all cases. We modified equation (6) by dividing the result by the size of the test sample and multiplied by 4π . This is accomplished in two steps:

Step 1: $n = \left(\frac{Z\sigma}{E}\right)^2$

Step 2: $n^* = \left(\frac{n}{k}\right)4\pi - (1 + \pi - 0.05)$ (15)

The result is 30 regardless of the length of k and the value of the test set: $\{k_1, k_2, \dots, k_T\}$. We randomly generated values between 0 and 100 for $n(test) = 10, 30, 50, 100, 200, 300, 400, 500$ and 1000 and produce the result of equation (15) as n[6] in Table 1.

Table 1. Randomly generated valued by Excel: RAND()*100 for equations 1, 2 & 3

	10	30	50	100	200	300	400	500	1,000
Z	1.65	1.65	1.65	1.65	1.65	1.65	1.65	1.65	1.65
Mean	47.73	49.36	53.85	48.32	50.64	52.35	48.41	47.86	50.79
SD	27.30	28.08	29.76	28.34	29.45	30.13	29.61	27.84	28.84
T(∞)	1.64	1.64	1.64	1.64	1.64	1.64	1.64	1.64	1.64
μ	33.57	40.95	46.95	43.67	47.23	49.49	45.99	45.81	49.29
σ	27.13	27.91	29.58	28.17	29.28	29.95	29.43	27.67	28.66
SE	8.58	5.10	4.18	2.82	2.07	1.73	1.47	1.24	0.91
n[6]*	27.23	81.68	136.13	272.25	544.5	816.75	1,089.00	1,361.25	2,722.50
n[8]	54.44	163.07	272.67	543.34	1,089.43	1,631.92	2,182.45	2,711.27	5,400.92
n[9]	1,308.77	985.14	945.56	898.98	897.05	894.38	965.61	760.47	756.06
n[15]	30.00	30.00	30.00	30.00	30.00	30.00	30.00	30.00	30.00

*n[6] is equation (6), n[8] is equation (8), and n[9] is equation (9) for continuous data. The result equation (14) is listed as n[14].

Following the same method for discrete data, if we used the initial test sample of $n = 100$. we fixed the initial test sample size for discrete data at 100 because this is the approximate number produced by equation (9) where the sample size is approximately equal to that of the discrete data under equation (6), being a general case. The result for equation (10) and (11) is 27.36 and 65.65, respectively. We assert that equation (9) under this condition produces approximately 30 and equation (11) is about twice that much (65.65). From our experiment in both cases of continuous

and discrete data, we assert that the approximate sample size is $n = 30$ without the need for correction factor: $(1 + \pi - 0.05)$ in equation (15).

Table 2. Power calculation for sample size

n_{test}	30	50	100	200	300	400	500	1,000
μ_1	40.95	46.95	43.67	47.23	49.49	45.99	45.81	49.29
μ_0	40.95	40.95	40.95	40.95	40.95	40.95	40.95	40.95
$\delta = \mu_1 - \mu_0$	-	6.00	2.72	6.28	8.54	5.04	4.86	8.34
σ	27.91	29.58	28.17	29.28	29.95	29.43	27.67	28.66
$1/n_0 = A$	0.03	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
$1/n_1 = B$	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
$\text{sqrt}(A+B) =$	0.23	0.17	0.12	0.09	0.08	0.07	0.05	0.04
C	6.45	5.12	3.45	2.67	2.29	1.97	1.52	1.28
$\sigma(C) = D$	1.65	1.65	1.65	1.65	1.65	1.65	1.65	1.65
Z^*	-	1.17	0.79	2.35	3.73	2.55	3.21	6.51
delta / D	1.65	0.48	0.86	0.70	2.08	0.90	1.56	4.86
Z								
$F(Z) =$	0.9514	0.6839	0.8056	0.7579	0.9824	0.8168	0.9410	1.0000
Power %								

Using equation (14) to obtain the Z score for power or $Z_{1-\beta}$ we are able to calculate the percentage probability of power by $F(Z)$. A propose sample of $n = 30$ could produce a power percentage probability of 0.9514. Under 0.95 confidence interval, we are satisfied with the power yielded by this sample size under equation (14). Experts are advocating a power of 0.90 for clinical trials (Wood and Lombert 1999, Writes 2002). Wood (1999) advocated a power calculation based on a significance test. In our experiment, we have achieved 0.9514 confidence interval. By industry standard, we have achieved the threshold to avoid Type II error.

5.0 CONCLUSION

We have example three methods for sample size determination for estimating confidence interval in continuous and discrete data. We found that these conventional methods (equations 1, 2, 3, 4 and 5) are unreliable. Different sizes of the initial test sample produce different final results of sample size. We made the correction to equation (6) and produce a new sample size equation where the calculation always produce $n = 30$. Discrete data is a special case where the initial test sample is larger. We used the initial test sample of the continuous data and look for the closest common sizes to represent initial test sample for discrete data. We found that initial test sample of 100 served this purpose. Our experiment also showed that the sample size for discrete data is also approximately 30 without the need for a correcting factor. We claim this new method for estimating sample size of $n = 30$ is a contribution to the field because we can verify that the sample size estimation, regardless of the size of initial test sample, has a stable result.

REFERENCES

- Bakan, David (1966). "The test of significance in psychological research." *Psychological Bulletin*. **66** (6): 423–437. doi:10.1037/h0020412. PMID 5974619.
- Browner, W.S., Newman T.B. (1987). "Are all significant P values created equal? The analogy between diagnostic tests and clinical research." *JAMA*; **257**: 2459-2463.
- Cox D.R., Hinkley D.V. (1974). *Theoretical Statistics*, Chapman & Hall, p. 49, p. 209.

- Devane D, Begley CM, Clarke M. (2004). “How many do I need? Basic principles of sample size estimation.” *J. Adv. Nursing*. **47**: 297–302.
- Fan, C. T.; Muller, Mervin E.; Rezuca, Ivan (1962-06-01). “Development of Sampling Plans by Using Sequential (Item by Item) Selection Techniques and Digital Computers.” *Journal of the American Statistical Association*. **57** (298): 387–402. doi:10.1080/01621459.1962.10480667. ISSN 0162-1459.
- Feller, W. (1968). *An Introduction to Probability Theory and Its Applications*. Volume 1. Wiley. Section VII.3. ISBN 0-471-25708-7.
- Fisher, R.A. (1925). *Statistical Methods for Research Workers*, Edinburgh: Oliver and Boyd, 1925, p.43.
- Fleiss, J.L. (1981). *Statistical methods for rates and proportions*, 2nd ed. New York, NY: Wiley; 45.
- Francis, J. J., Johnston, M., Robertson, C., Glidewell, L., Entwistle, V., Eccles, M. P., & Grimshaw, J. M. (2010). “What is an adequate sample size? Operationalising data saturation for theory-based interview studies.” *Psychology and Health*, **25**, 1229–1245. doi:10.1080/08870440903194015.
- Freiman J.A., T.C. Chalmers, H. Smith, R.R. Kuebler (1978). “The importance of beta, the type II error and sample size in the design and interpretation of the randomized control trial: survey of 71 —negative trials.” *N. Engl. J. Med.*, **299**: 690-694.
- Fugard A.J.B.; Potts H.W.W. (10 February 2015). “Supporting thinking on sample sizes for thematic analyses: A quantitative tool.” *International Journal of Social Research Methodology*. **18** (6): 669–684. doi:10.1080/13645579.2015.1005453.
- Galvin R (2015). “How many interviews are enough? Do qualitative interviews in building energy consumption research produce reliable knowledge?” *Journal of Building Engineering*, **1**: 2–12.
- Glaser, B. (1965). “The constant comparative method of qualitative analysis.” *Social Problems*. **12**, 436–445.
- Gogtay, Nithya J. (2010). “Principles of sample size calculation.” *Indian J. Ophthalmol*. 2010 Nov-Dec; **58**(6): 517–518. doi: 10.4103/0301-4738.71692
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC2993982/>
- Guest, G., Bunce, A., & Johnson, L. (2006). “How many interviews are enough?: An experiment with data saturation and variability.” *Field Methods*, **18**, 59–82. doi:10.1177/1525822X05279903
- Greenland, Sander; Senn, Stephen J.; Rothman, Kenneth J.; Carlin, John B.; Poole, Charles; Goodman, Steven N.; Altman, Douglas G. (April 2016). “Statistical tests, P values, confidence intervals, and power: a guide to misinterpretations.” *European Journal of Epidemiology*. **31** (4): 337–350. doi:10.1007/s10654-016-0149-3. ISSN 0393-2990. PMC 4877414. PMID 27209009.
- Gupta S.C. and V.K. Kapoor (1970). *Fundamental of mathematical statistics*, SC Publication, New Delhi, India.
- Hans Jürgen Prömel (2005). “Complete Disorder is Impossible: The Mathematical Work of Walter Deuber.” *Combinatorics, Probability and Computing*. Cambridge University Press. **14**: 3–16. doi:10.1017/S0963548304006674.
- Moher D., C.S. Dulberg, G.A. Wells (1994). “Statistical power, sample size, and their reporting in randomized controlled trials.” *JAMA*, **272**: 122-124.
- Israel, Glen D. (1992). “Determining Sample Size.” Fact Sheet PEOD-6; November 1992.
http://sociology.soc.uoc.gr/socmedia/papageo/metaptyxiakoi/sample_size/samplesize1.pdf
- Israel, Glenn D. (1992). *Sampling the Evidence of Extension Program Impact*. Program Evaluation and Organizational Development, IFAS, University of Florida.
- Julios S.A. (2004). “Sample sizes for clinical trials with normal data.” *Stats Med*. **23**: 1921–86.
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/15195324>

- Karla Hemming, Alan J. Girling, Alice Stieh, Jenifer Marsh and Richard J. Lilford (2011). "Sample size calculations for cluster randomized controlled trials with a fixed number of clusters." *BMC Medical Research Methodology*, **11**, 102.
- Kendall, M.G. and Stuart, D.G. (1973). *The Advanced Theory of Statistics*. Vol 2: Inference and Relationship, Griffin, London. Section 20.4.
- Kish, Leslie (1965). *Survey Sampling*. New York: John Wiley and Sons, Inc. p. 78-94
- Mayo, D. G. (1981). "In defence of the Neyman–Pearson theory of confidence intervals," *Philosophy of Science*, **48** (2), 269–280. JSTOR 187185.
- Meng, Xiangrui (2013). "Scalable Simple Random Sampling and Stratified Sampling" (PDF). *Proceedings of the 30th International Conference on Machine Learning (ICML-13)*: 531–539.
- Miaoulis, George, and R. D. Michener (1976). *An Introduction to Sampling*. Dubuque, Iowa: Kendall/Hunt Publishing Company.
- Neyman, J. (1937). "Outline of a Theory of Statistical Estimation Based on the Classical Theory of Probability." *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society A*. **236** (767): 333–380. Bibcode:1937RSPTA.236..333N. doi:10.1098/rsta.1937.0005. JSTOR 91337.
- Nuzzo, Regina (2014). "Scientific method: Statistical errors." *Nature*. **506** (7487): 150–152. Bibcode:2014Natur.506..150N. doi:10.1038/506150a. PMID 24522584.
- Onwuegbuzie, A. J., & Leech, N. L. (2007). "A call for qualitative power analyses." *Quality & Quantity*. **41**, 105–121. doi:10.1007/s11135-005-1098-1
- Papoulis, Athanasios; Pillai, S. Unnikrishna (2002). *Probability, Random Variables, and Stochastic Processes* (4th ed.). Boston: McGraw-Hill. ISBN 0-07-122661-3.
- Rice, John A. (2007). *Mathematical Statistics and Data Analysis* (3rd ed.). Thomson Brooks/Cole. §9.3.
- Rosner B (2000). *Fundamentals of biostatistics*, 5th ed. Pacific Grove, Calif: Duxbury, 308.
- Sandelowski, M. (1995). "Sample size in qualitative research." *Research in Nursing & Health*, **18**, 179–183.
- Sathian B., Jaydevan Sreedharan, Suresh N. Babu, Krishna Sharan, E. S. Abhilash, E. Rajesh (2010). "Relevance of sample size determination in medical research." *Nepal Journal of Epidemiology*, **1** (1).
- Schulz, K. F., D. G. Altman, and D. Moher (2010): "CONSORT 2010 Statement: updated guidelines for reporting parallel group randomised trials," *BMJ*, 340.
- Shah Hitesh (2011). "How to calculate sample size in an animal study." *Natl. J. Physiol. Pharmacol.*, **1** (1), 35 -39.
- Singh A.S., M.B. Masuku (2012). "An insight statistical techniques and design in agricultural and applied research." *World Jr. of Agricultural Sciences*, **8**(6), 568-584.
- Smith, M. F. (1983). "Sampling Considerations," *In Evaluating Cooperative Extension Programs. Florida Cooperative Extension Service Bulletin PE-1*. Institute of Food and Agricultural Sciences. University of Florida.
- Stuart A., Ord K., Arnold S. (1999), *Kendall's Advanced Theory of Statistics: Volume 2A—Classical Inference & the Linear Model* (Arnold) §20.2.
- Sudman, Seymour. (1976). *Applied Sampling*. New York: Academic Press.
- Sunter, A. B. (1977-01-01). "List Sequential Sampling with Equal or Unequal Probabilities without Replacement." *Applied Statistics*. **26** (3): 261–268. doi:10.2307/2346966. JSTOR 2346966.
- Triola, Mario (2001). *Elementary statistics* (8 ed.). Boston: Addison-Wesley. p. 388. ISBN 978-0-201-61477-0.
- Vitter, Jeffrey S. (1985-03-01). "Random Sampling with a Reservoir." *ACM Trans. Math. Softw.* **11** (1): 37–57. CiteSeerX 10.1.1.138.784. doi:10.1145/3147.3165. ISSN 0098-3500.
- Wood J. and M. Lambert (1999). "Sample size calculations for trials in health services research." *J. Health Ser. Res. Policy*, **4** (4): 226 – 9.

- Wright, A., Maloney, F. L., & Feblowitz, J. C. (2011). "Clinician attitudes toward and use of electronic problem lists: a thematic analysis." *BMC Medical Informatics and Decision Making*, **11**, 36. doi:10.1186/1472-6947-11-36
- Yamane, Taro (1967). *Statistics, An Introductory Analysis*, 2nd Ed., New York: Harper and Row; p. 886.
- Zodpey, S.P. (2004). "Sample size and power analysis in medical research." *Indian J. Dermatol. Venereol. Leprol*, **70** (2), 123-128.